

Synthesis and spectroscopic studies of some mixed ligand complexes of titanium(IV)

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Abstract : Some new titanium(IV) complexes with alkyl xanthates of the type $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ti}_2(\eta^2\text{-S}_2\text{COR})_2\text{Cl}_4]$ (1), $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ti}_2(\eta^2\text{-S}_2\text{COR})_4\text{Cl}_2]$ (2) and $[\text{ClTi}(\eta^2\text{-S}_2\text{COR})_3]$ (3) have been synthesized by simple metathetic reaction. The complexes $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ti}_2(\eta^2\text{-S}_2\text{COR})_2\text{Cl}_4]$ have been further treated with sodium salts of Schiff bases (derived from isatin and aniline) and sodium tetraisopropoxyaluminate to produce mixed ligand complexes of the type $[(\text{sb})\text{TiCl}_2(\eta^2\text{-S}_2\text{COR})]$ (4) and $[(\eta^2\text{-S}_2\text{COR})\text{TiCl}_2(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_2\}]$ (5). All these complexes are characterized by elemental analysis (Ti, C, H, N, S and Cl) and spectroscopic data, i.e. UV-Visible, IR, NMR (^1H and ^{13}C) and FAB-MS studies. The above data due to the metal binding sites of the ligands suggested coordination number six for complexes 1, 2, 4 and 5 and coordination 5 for complex 3, tentatively.

Keywords : Chloro-Ti^{IV}-alkyl xanthate, Schiff base, mixed ligand complexes.

Introduction

The bidentate xanthate ligand by virtue of its low charge and relative small size is particularly well suited for stabilization of higher coordination states of metals^{1,2}. The chemistry of metal xanthates is quite extensive although complexes with group '4' metals^{3,4} are limited and showed microbial activity⁵. We report herein the synthesis and characterization of some mixed ligand complexes of titanium(IV) with - chloride, alkyl xanthate, Schiff bases and aluminium-isopropoxide and their spectroscopic characterization.

Results and discussion

The reaction of titanium tetrachloride with potassium alkyl xanthates in 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 molar ratios, respectively (in THF/benzene mixture) yielded complexes of the type $[\text{Cl}_3\text{Ti}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})]$, $[\text{Cl}_2\text{Ti}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})_2]$ and $[\text{ClTi}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})_3]$ according to the following equations :

where, R = C₂H₅ (E.Xan), C₃H₇ (P.Xan), C₄H₉ (B.Xan)

The trichlorotitanium(IV) alkyl xanthate complexes have been treated with sodium salts of Schiff bases (such as NaSIA and NaSIN) and sodium tetraisopropoxyaluminate (in THF/benzene mixture). The reaction mixture was refluxed for about six hours and the mixed ligand complexes of the types - $[\text{Cl}_2\text{Ti}(\text{Xan})(\text{SIA})]$, $[\text{Cl}_2\text{Ti}(\text{Xan})(\text{SIN})]$ and $[\text{Cl}_2\text{Ti}(\text{Xan})\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}]$ were obtained. It can be shown by the following chemical equations :

where, Xan = E.Xan, P.Xan and B.Xan; sb = SIA and SIN

All these complexes, synthesized during the course of present investigations, are coloured and soluble in chloroform, THF, DMSO and DMF. These complexes are hygroscopic in nature and decompose very slowly at room temperature but remain intact when stored in dry and cold conditions.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of all the complexes exhibited a single charge-transfer band in the region 23000–24800 cm^{-1} in accordance with the electronic configuration $(n-1)d^0ns^0$ of the metal⁶.

Infrared spectra :

The xanthate ligands, behave as a monodentate or bidentate fashion and exhibit four characteristic bands at ~ 1250 , 1100, 1060 and 550 cm^{-1} , corresponding $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$, $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{S}}$, $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{R}-\text{O}}$ vibrations, respectively⁸. The band at 1250 cm^{-1} has about 90% contribution for C–O–R stretch and 10% for C=S stretch. The band around 1060 cm^{-1} has a single major contribution of 60% from the C=S stretch⁹. The band at 1060–1070 cm^{-1} was observed due to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$ vibrations which support the following resonance forms (a) and (b) :

The infra-red stretching frequencies^{10–14} observed in titanium(IV) complexes due to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$ stretch was observed in the region 1070–1065 cm^{-1} , lower shift ($\sim 25 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in comparison to ligand spectra indicating coordination through sulphur. The bands observed around 331–320 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{Ti}-\text{S}}$ ¹⁰, whereas frequency due to $\nu_{\text{Ti}-\text{Cl}}$ was observed at 358–348 cm^{-1} in the complexes¹¹.

The band appeared at 1628–1624 cm^{-1} in the ligands due to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ ¹⁴ was shifted to lower frequency 1613–1604 cm^{-1} in the complexes indicating coordination through azomethine nitrogen to the titanium metal. The band observed at around 1272–1268 cm^{-1} may be attributed to the $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}}$ stretching frequency, which was shifted to higher frequency region suggesting the bonding through oxygen. Coordination of nitrogen to titanium has been indicated by the appearance of new band at 397 cm^{-1} in their IR spectra which may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{Ti}-\text{N}}$. The bands at 430–500 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu_{\text{Ti}-\text{O}}$ and band at around 335–320 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{Ti}-\text{S}}$. The alkoxy-bridged (bimetallic) complexes exhibited characteristic frequencies for metal-alkoxy group $\nu_{(\text{C}-\text{O})\text{M}}$ in the region 1160–1127 cm^{-1} for terminal isopropoxy group and 990–950 cm^{-1} has been assigned for bridging isopropoxy groups. The band observed at 620–600 cm^{-1} has been assigned for $\nu_{\text{Al}-\text{O}}$.

¹H NMR spectra :

The titanium(IV) complexes, studied herein exhibit little variation in chemical shifts of the protons on the OR groups present due to the delocalization of electrons between O–CS₂ of the ligand and titanium metal. The observed data shows good agreement with the corresponding alkyl groups¹⁵ deshielded on complexation, a slight down field shifts in the position of the resonance signals of various protons in the complexes were also observed due to change in the electronic environment (deshielding) around the protons in the ligands on coordination with the metal atom. A comparison of the spectra of ligands with those of complexes, showed a peak at 11.2 ppm due to NH of isatin ring in the spectra of ligands which disappears after coordination. The chemical shifts due to aromatic protons appear at 7.8–8.4 ppm in the ligands which shifted slightly downfield in the complexes¹⁶. The methine protons of the terminal and bridging isopropoxy groups were observed at 3.90–3.99 and 4.06–4.25 ppm, respectively. While the corresponding methyl protons are observed in the region 1.15–1.19 and 1.19–1.22 ppm as a doublet, indicating that these are magnetically nonequivalent.

¹³C NMR spectra :

The carbon signal due to the presence of –CS₂ group appears at δ 163.0 in ligands which shifts down field in the complexes probably showing the bidentate nature of the CS₂ group. The shifting of carbon signals of –C=N (δ 159) to down field in the complexes suggesting the bonding through azomethine group. The signals of methyl carbon due to the presence of terminal and bridging isopropoxy groups are observed at 23.91–25.15 and 25.11–26.02 ppm respectively, while methine carbons of the terminal and the bridging isopropoxy groups are observed at 60.18–60.52 ppm and 61.16–64.42 ppm respectively. The presence of two types of signals for methyl and methine carbons further support the fact observed in ¹H NMR spectra showing magnetically nonequivalence.

FAB-mass spectra :

The FAB-mass spectra^{17–19} some characteristic molecular ion peaks showed characteristics for these complexes, which convincingly support the composition of new complexes. The spectra of [Cl₃Ti(S₂COC₂H₅)₂]₂ and [Cl₂Ti(S₂COC₂H₅)₂]₂ complexes showed peak at *m/z* 550 and 722 respectively, which correspond to the molecular weight of the complex in their dimeric form, while, [ClTi(S₂COC₂H₅)₃] complex showed a peak at *m/z* 446 corresponds to the molecular weight of the complex in its monomeric form.

The spectral data suggest that the xanthate ligands act as monobasic, bidentate chelating agents, coordinating through two sulphur atoms. For, $[\text{Cl}_3\text{Ti}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})]$ and $[\text{Cl}_2\text{Ti}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})_2]$ complexes, IR spectral data and FAB-mass data suggest molecular association, and chloro-bridged structure may be proposed for these complexes, $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ti}_2(\eta^2\text{-S}_2\text{COR})_2\text{Cl}_4]$ and $[(\text{sb})\text{TiCl}_2(\eta^2\text{-S}_2\text{COR})]$. The fragmentation pattern (Scheme 1) and spectrum (Fig. 1) of the complex $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ti}_2(\eta^2\text{-S}_2\text{COC}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Cl}_4]$ are given as one of the representative.

Schiff bases [isatin-aniline (SIA) and isatin-2-nitroaniline (SIN)]¹⁸ and sodium tetraalkoxyaluminate were prepared by the reported method. Chloride, titanium¹⁹ and sulphur²⁰ were estimated following literature method. Elemental analyses of C, H, N were carried out on a Perkin-Elmer series II model 2400. The electronic spectra of the compound were recorded in dimethyl formamide using 10 mm quartz cell on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 15 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The infrared spectra in the range 4000–200 cm^{-1} were recorded in KBr pellets on Perkin-

Scheme 1. FAB-mass fragmentation pattern of complex $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ti}_2(\eta^2\text{-S}_2\text{COC}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Cl}_4]$.

Fig. 1. FAB-mass spectra of complex $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ti}_2(\eta^2\text{-S}_2\text{COC}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Cl}_4]$.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All the solvents and reagent were used as received without any further purification. The alkylxanthates²,

Elmer 1000 FTIR spectrophotometer. The NMR spectra were recorded in deuterated chloroform on Bruker DRX-300 spectrometer at the sweep width of 300 MHz and a sweep time of 300 s. The FAB-mass spectra were recorded

on a Jeol SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/data system using Argon/Xenon (6 kV, 10 mV) as the FAB gas.

To a solution of titanium tetrachloride (0.269 g, 1.42 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran (20 ml) a solution of ethyl xanthate (E.Xan) (0.228 g, 1.42 mmol) in benzene (mixed with THF) was added with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was allowed to reflux for ~2 h. The solution was filtered and filtrate was concentrated by distillation under reduced pressure. The product so obtained was purified by recrystallization from THF-benzene mixture (purity was further checked by TLC) to afford light yellow coloured crystals (Found : C, 13.24; H, 1.90; Cl, 38.91; S, 23.48; Ti, 17.4. Calcd. for $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{Cl}_6\text{O}_2\text{S}_4\text{Ti}_2$: C, 13.08; H, 1.83; Cl, 38.62; S, 23.28; Ti, 17.38%).

A benzene solution of ethyl xanthate (0.638 g, 4.00 mmol) containing THF was added with constant stirring to a solution of titanium tetrachloride (0.379 g, 2.00 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran (~20 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for ~3 h. The product so obtained was filtered and concentrated by distillation and dried *in vacuo*. It was further recrystallized from THF-benzene mixture (purity was further checked by TLC) to afford light yellow coloured crystals (Found : C, 20.01; H, 2.91; Cl, 20.60; S, 35.62; Ti, 13.36. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{Cl}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}_8\text{Ti}_2$: C, 19.95; H, 2.79; Cl, 19.63; S, 35.51; Ti, 13.25%).

A solution of ethyl xanthate (0.84 g, 5.25 mmol) (in benzene-THF mixture) was added to a solution of titanium tetrachloride (0.332 g, 1.75 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran (~20 ml) with constant stirring and was refluxed for ~4 h. The resulting light yellow coloured solution was filtered and the excess solvent was distilled off. The product was purified by recrystallized from THF-benzene mixture (Found : C, 24.31; H, 3.69; Cl, 8.01; S, 43.62; Ti, 10.36. Calcd. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{15}\text{ClO}_3\text{S}_6\text{Ti}$: C, 24.19; H, 3.38; Cl, 7.93; S, 43.05; Ti, 10.71%).

To a stirred hot suspension of sodium salt of isatin-aniline (0.377 g, 1.70 mmol) THF/benzene mixture of the titanium ethyl xanthate (0.408 g, 1.70 mmol) was added. The mixture was refluxed for ~6 h with constant stirring. The resulting light reddish coloured solution was filtered. The filtrate was concentrated and dried under reduced pressure. The product so obtained was recrystallized in THF-benzene mixture (Found : C, 44.32; H,

3.19; Cl, 15.21; N, 6.17; S, 13.99; Ti, 10.39. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}_2\text{Ti}$: C, 44.27; H, 3.06; Cl, 15.37; N, 6.07; S, 13.90; Ti, 10.38%).

A similar synthetic procedure was adopted for reactions of titanium alkyl xanthates with other Schiff bases such as isatin-2-nitroaniline (SIN).

To a stirred hot solution of titanium(IV) ethyl xanthate (0.259 g, 1.08 mmol) in THF (~40 ml) a benzene (~30 ml) solution of sodium tetraisopropoxyaluminate (0.24 g 1.08 mmol) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred for ~2 h followed by refluxing for 5 h. The light yellow coloured precipitate was filtered and dried under reduced pressure. The complex was further crystallized by THF-benzene mixture (Found : C, 35.93; H, 6.69; Cl, 14.22; S, 12.98; Ti, 9.62. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{33}\text{AlCl}_2\text{O}_5\text{S}_2\text{Ti}$: C, 35.80; H, 6.61; Cl, 14.09; S, 12.74; Ti, 9.51%).

The reactions of titanium(IV) propyl xanthate and titanium(IV) butyl xanthate with sodium tetraalkoxyaluminate was also treated by above given method.

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